

Supplementary table 1. Model Parameters for Cost-effectiveness Analysis

Model Parameter	Point estimate	Distirbution	Source.
Transition probabilities			
NoPain → Acute Pain (annual)	0.186	Beta (531.63, 143.07)	Cassidy et al. (1)
Acute Pain → Chronic Pain	0.32	Beta (1667, 3568)	Stevans et al. (2)
Chronic Pain → No Pain (annual probability)	0.420	Beta (138.13, 256.53)	Costa et al. (3)
All-cause mortality (6 months)	Age-specific	Deterministic	Yucatán life tables (4)
SCM effects			
SCM effect on Acute → Chronic transition	RR = 0.90	Lognormal (log 0.90, 0.0569)	Assumption informed by intervention
SCM effect on Chronic → No Pain transition	RR = 1.05	Lognormal (log 1.05, 0.0243)	Assumption informed by intervention
Utilities			
Utility: No Pain	0.964 (SD 0.117)	Beta (1.45, 0.05)	Argentine EQ-5D valuation (5)
Utility: Acute Pain	0.751 (SD 0.181)	Beta (3.54, 1.17)	Argentine EQ-5D valuation (5)
Utility: Chronic Pain	0.714 (SD 0.237)	Beta (1.88, 0.75)	Argentine EQ-5D valuation (5)
Costs			
CAU cost per 6-month cycle	75.08 USD	Gamma (shape = 25, scale = 3.00)	Study costing
SCM cost per 6-month cycle (10-year horizon)	51.60 USD	Gamma (shape = 25, scale = 2.06)	Study costing

Supplementary table 2. Transition matrix

From/to	No pain	Acute pain	Chronic pain	Death
No pain	$1 - (p_{NtA} + p_M)$	0.186 ^a	0	p_M
Acute pain	$1 - (p_{AtC} + p_M)$	0	$0.320^b \times SCMe^d$	p_M
Chronic pain	$0.238^c \times SCMe^e$	0	$1 - (p_{CtN} + p_M)$	p_M
Death	0	0	0	1

pNtA: Probability of transitioning from No Pain to Acute Pain, *pAtC*: Probability of transitioning from Acute Pain to Chronic Pain, *pCtN*: Probability of transitioning from Chronic Pain to No Pain.

pM: Probability of death obtained from Yucatan life tables. (4)

a: Cassidy et al. (1)

b: Stevans et al. (2)

c: Costa et al. (3). Yearly probability converted to 6 months

d: Syndemic Care Model effect estimated at RR 1.10

e: Syndemic Care Model effect estimated at RR 0.90

References:

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